

1 Supplementary Information

2 **Clone-specific phenotypic plasticity under constant darkness and competition reveals surprising**
3 **aphid resilience**

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28 **Statement of contribution**

29 All authors wrote the manuscript.

30 **Yim Zhe Yang (YZY)** contributed to the design of the experiment, co-performed the experiment with MSK,
31 conducted the metabolomics and protein analyses, and produced the manuscript with MSK.

32 **Mouhammad Shadi Khudr (MSK)** conceived and designed the experiment, co-performed the experiment
33 with YZY, envisioned the analyses, did the statistical analysis, and visualised the data. MSK produced the
34 manuscript with YZY.

35 **Conrado Guerrero Quiles (CGQ)** did the protein analysis with YZY and provided interpretations of the
36 protein data.

37 **Hawa Jahan (HJ)** did the C:N analysis and provided interpretations for the C:N data. HJ also provided
38 insights on the interpretation of the results and the endosymbiont communities of the pea aphids.

39 **Abdullatif Alfutimie (AA)** provided guidance and insights on the metabolomics analysis and contributed
40 to the writing and production of the final draft of the manuscript.

41 **Reinmar Hager (RH)** hosted the work and provided insights on the development of the analyses and the
42 manuscript. RH contributed to the enrichment of the manuscript.

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Fig S1. Experimental design. We used three aphid clones (pea aphids [N116 and N127], and black bean aphid [BB]) that were respectively raised on individual faba bean hosts. There were two regimes: The main experimental system was deprived of light rhythmicity, *i.e.*, both the host plants (sown, grown, and infested) and the aphids were raised under complete darkness (0h Day:24h Night). In total there were 360 aphids = Alone as a single clone (3 aphid clones X 6 repeats X 10 aphid 2nd instars per microcosm) + Competition (3 competition scenarios X 6 repeats X [5+5] aphid 2nd instars per microcosm). The reference experimental system was the control under a normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night). Phenotypically for aphid interactions, the design was fully factorial. However, for the main text, we focused on two sub-sets. In the first, aphids were respectively present in the microcosm as single clones. In the second sub-set, the target pea-aphid clone N116 was either alone or in intraspecific competition with a conspecific (N127) or interspecific competition with a heterospecific (BB). The experiment lasted for 11 days following aphid introduction to respective 12-day-old host plants. See main text Methods for supportive details.

Table S1. Model (glm1), a test of aphid reproductive success under normal dark/light conditions or complete darkness (lack of light rhythmicity). Analysis of deviance table (Type II tests) displaying the significance of the main effects tested in the Model (glm1) as specified in the main text Methods. The predictors were: Light regime (a categorical variable of two levels (Light [baseline], and constant darkness), Aphid clone (a categorical variable of three levels (pea aphid N116 [baseline], pea aphid N127, black bean aphid BB), The interaction (Light regime X Aphid clone), and SRW (shoot dry weight to root dry weight ratio, a numerical variable, a covariate). Aphid reproductive success (total aphid numbers in the microcosm on Day 11, representing aphid reproductive success) was the response variable. Significant results are shown in bold.

	Sum Sq	Df	F value	Pr(>F)
SRW	173.26	1	5.49	0.03
Light regime	45.91	1	1.45	0.241
Aphid clone	418.95	2	6.63	0.006
Light regime X Aphid clone	457.47	2	7.24	0.004
Residuals	631.6	20		

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79 **Fig S2. Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) spectra of pea aphid (N116) in response to**
 80 **normal dark/light conditions or complete darkness (lack of light rhythmicity).** The upper panel
 81 represents the metabolomic response of the pea aphid clone (N116) when it was alone as a single clone
 82 in the microcosm on its faba bean host plant under a normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night). Whereas,
 83 the lower panel represents the pea aphid clone (N116) when it was alone as a single clone in the
 84 microcosm on its faba bean host plant under constant darkness (0h Day:24h Night). The FTIRs were taken
 85 following the end of the experiment on Day 11. Refer to the main text Methods for further specifications.

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Fig S3. Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) spectra of pea aphid (N127) in response to normal dark/light conditions or complete darkness (lack of light rhythmicity). The upper panel represents the metabolomic response of the pea aphid clone (N127) when it was alone as a single clone in the microcosm on its faba bean host plant under a normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night). Whereas, the lower panel represents the pea aphid clone (N127) when it was alone as a single clone in the microcosm on its faba bean host plant under constant darkness (0h Day:24h Night). The FTIRs were taken following the end of the experiment on Day 11. Refer to the main text Methods for further specifications.

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Fig S4. Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) spectra of pea aphid (BB) in response to normal dark/light conditions or complete darkness (lack of light rhythmicity). The upper panel represents the metabolomic response of the pea aphid clone (BB) when it was alone as a single clone in the microcosm on its faba bean host plant under a normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night). Whereas, the lower panel represents the pea aphid clone (BB) when it was alone as a single clone in the microcosm on its faba bean host plant under constant darkness (0h Day:24h Night). The FTIRs were taken following the end of the experiment on Day 11. Refer to the main text Methods for further specifications.

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Fig S5. Faba bean host plant and aphids, with and without complete darkness (lack of light rhythmicity). Panel (A) represents the faba bean host plant under a normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night). Panel (B) represents the deformed (etiolated) host plant under constant darkness (0h Day:24h Night). Panel (C) represents the aphid-infested deformed host plant under constant darkness (0h Day:24h Night) at the end of the experiment on Day 11. Panel (D) represents a close-up shot of the N127-infested deformed host plant under constant darkness (0h Day:24h Night) at the end of the experiment on Day 11. Panel (E) represents the green pea aphid clone (N116) under a normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night) at the end of the experiment on Day 11. Panel (F) represents the green pea aphid clone (N116) under constant darkness (0h Day:24h Night) at the end of the experiment on Day 11. Panel (G) represents the pink pea aphid clone (N127) under a normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night) at the end of the experiment on Day 11. Panel (H) represents the pink pea aphid clone (N127) under constant darkness (0h Day:24h Night). Panel (I) represents the black bean aphid (BB) under a normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night) at the end of the experiment on Day 11. Panel (H) represents the black bean aphid (BB) under constant darkness (0h Day:24h Night) on Day 11.

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Fig S6. Aphid body colour analysis in response to normal dark/light conditions or complete darkness (lack of light rhythmicity). Using Leica M205 FA fluorescence stereomicroscope, we analysed the body colour of aphids when they were respectively present in the microcosm as respective single clones on the faba bean host under normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night), referred to as (L), and constant darkness (0h Day:24h Night), referred to as (NL). We used two pea aphid clones (N116 and N127) and one clone of black bean aphid (BB).

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Fig S7. Plant chlorophyll analysis in response to aphid infestation. Using USB4000 UV-Vis Fiber Optic Spectrometer, we analysed the chlorophyll types of the faba bean host plant, with and without respective infestation with single aphid clones, under a normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night). The aphids were present on the faba bean host in the microcosm alone as respective single clones. We used two pea aphid clones (N116 and N127) and one clone of black bean aphid (BB), plant only refers to the aphid-free control. Leaf samples were pooled from each of the three replicates per treatment with three readings on the spectrometer; the mean (\pm SE) of the readings is shown per chlorophyll type. The average ratios of chlorophyll A:chlorophyll B were as follows: 1.67 (plant only), 1.57 (N116), 2.39 (N127), and 1.63 (BB).

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Fig S8. C:N ratios in the host plant and aphids in response to normal dark/light conditions or complete darkness (lack of light rhythmicity). The bars represent the values of C:N ratios of the faba bean host plant (left) and aphids (right); normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night), referred to as (L), and constant darkness (0h Day:24h Night), referred to as (NL). Three aphid clones (pea aphids [N116 and N127] and black bean aphids [BB]) were respectively present in the microcosm as respective single clones on the faba bean host.

159 **Table S2. Model (GLM2), a test of N116 reproductive success in response to normal dark/light**
 160 **conditions or complete darkness (lack of light rhythmicity) with and without competition.** Analysis
 161 of deviance table (Type II tests) displaying the significance of the main effects tested in the Model (GLM2)
 162 as specified in the main text Methods. The predictors were: Light regime (a categorical variable of two
 163 levels (Light [baseline], and constant darkness), Clonal interaction status (a categorical variable of three
 164 levels (pea aphid clone N116 alone as a single clone [baseline], N116 competing against pea aphid clone
 165 N127 [intraspecific competition], or against black bean aphid clone BB [interspecific competition]), The
 166 interaction (Light regime X Clonal interaction status), SRW (shoot dry weight to root dry weight ratio, a
 167 numerical variable, a covariate), and Competitor density (a numerical variable representing the total
 168 numbers of the respective aphid clone competing with N116). 2). N116 reproductive success (total aphid
 169 numbers in the microcosm) was the response variable. Significant results are shown in bold.

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	Sum Sq	Df	F value	Pr(>F)
SRW	0.54	1	0.02	0.893
Competitive density	6.12	1	0.21	0.652
Light regime	332.55	1	11.43	0.003
Clonal interaction status	162.99	2	2.80	0.086
Light regime X Clonal interaction status	57.89	2	0.995	0.388
Residuals	552.64	19		

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187 **Fig S9. Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) spectra of pea aphids (N116 and N127) in**
188 **response to normal dark/light conditions and intraspecific competition.** The upper panel represents
189 the metabolomic response of the pea aphid clone (N116) when it competed against the conspecific (N127)
190 on the faba bean host under a normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night). Whereas, the lower panel
191 represents the pea aphid clone (N127) when it competed against (N116) on the faba bean host under a
192 normal light-dark cycle. The FTIRs were taken following the end of the experiment on Day 11. Refer to the
193 main text Methods for further specifications.

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Fig S10. Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) spectra of pea aphids (N116 and N127 in response to complete darkness (lack of light rhythmicity) and interspecific competition. The upper panel represents the metabolomic response of the pea aphid clone (N116) when it competed against the conspecific (N127) on the faba bean host under constant darkness (0h Day:24h Night). Whereas, the lower panel represents the pea aphid clone (N127) when it competed against (N116) on the faba bean host under constant darkness. The FTIRs were taken following the end of the experiment on Day 11. Refer to the main text Methods for further specifications.

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212 **Fig S11. Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) spectra of pea aphid (N116) and black**
 213 **bean aphid (BB) in response to normal dark/light conditions and interspecific competition.** The
 214 upper panel represents the metabolomic response of the pea aphid clone (N116) when it competed against
 215 the heterospecific (BB) on the faba bean host under a normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night).
 216 Whereas, the lower panel represents the black bean aphid clone (BB) when it competed against (N116)
 217 on the faba bean host under a normal light-dark cycle. The FTIRs were taken following the end of the
 218 experiment on Day 11. Refer to the main text Methods for further specifications.

Fig S12. Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) spectra of pea aphid (N116) and black bean aphid (BB) in response to complete darkness (lack of light rhythmicity) and interspecific competition. The upper panel represents the metabolomic response of the pea aphid clone (N116) when it competed against the heterospecific (BB) on the faba bean plant under constant darkness (0h Day:24h Night). Whereas, the lower panel represents the black bean aphid clone (BB) when it competed against (N116) on the faba bean host under constant darkness. The FTIRs were taken following the end of the experiment on Day 11. Refer to the main text Methods for further specifications.

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234 **Fig S13. Aphid body colour analysis in response to normal dark/light conditions or complete**
235 **darkness (lack of light rhythmicity).** Using Leica M205 FA fluorescence stereomicroscope, we analysed
236 the body colour of aphids when the clones were respectively present in the microcosm as single clones
237 on the faba bean host under normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night), referred to as (L), and constant
238 darkness (0h Day:24h Night), referred to as (NL). We used two pea aphid clones (N116 and N127) and
239 one clone of black bean aphid (BB).

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248 **Fig S14. Plant chlorophyll analysis in response to aphid infestation with N116 alone or in**
249 **competition.** Using USB4000 UV-Vis Fiber Optic Spectrometer, we analysed the chlorophyll types of the
250 faba bean host plant, with and without respective infestation with the target pea aphid clone N116 when it
251 was present in the microcosm alone as a single clone, or in intraspecific competition with (N127), or
252 interspecific competition with black bean aphid (BB), under normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night).
253 Leaf samples were pooled from each of the three replicates per treatment with three readings on the
254 spectrometer; the mean of the readings is shown per chlorophyll type. Plant only refers to the aphid-free
255 control. The mean (\pm SE) of the readings is shown per chlorophyll type. The average ratios of chlorophyll
256 A:chlorophyll B were as follows: 1.67 (plant only), 1.57 (N116), 2.17 (intraspecific competition [N116 vs
257 N127]), and 2.91 (interspecific competition [N116 vs BB]).

Fig S15. C:N ratios in the host plant and the pea aphid clone (N116) in response to normal dark/light conditions or complete darkness (lack of light rhythmicity) and competition. The bars represent the values of C:N ratios of the faba bean host plant (left) and the pea aphid clone (N116) (right); normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night), referred to as (L), and constant darkness (0h Day:24h Night), referred to as (NL). N116 was present on the faba bean host in the microcosm either alone as respective single clones, or in intraspecific competition with N127, referred to as (vs N127), or in interspecific competition with black bean aphid (BB), referred to as (vs BB).

Note 1: Analysis of aphid reproductive success, C:N ratios and plant traits across all clones subject to competition

We present below the outcome of the reproductive success of each aphid clone with and without competition (Fig. S16). We applied a generalised linear model (GLM3) to test the reproductive success of the respective aphid clones (aphid total numbers in the microcosm on the 11th day), (Table S3). We also display the corresponding C:N ratios of the aphids and the host plant per scenario of interaction (Fig. S17). Further, we applied generalised linear models (GLM4 [Table S4], GLM5 [Table S5], and GLM6 [Table S6]) to examine the host plant traits (total plant dry weight, the difference in the shoot length between the beginning and the end of the experiment, and the shoot length to root length ratio at the end of the experiment, respectively). We also display the corresponding C:N ratios of the aphids and the host plant per scenario of interaction (Fig. S17) as well as the said plant traits (Figs. S18-S20). The statistical analysis was done in R version 4.0.4 (R Core Team 2021), 'multcomp' package (Hothorn et al. 2008); the main effects of the model are shown using an Anova command, R package 'car' (Fox and Weisberg 2019).

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290 **Fig S16. Aphid reproductive success under normal dark/light conditions or complete darkness,**
 291 **subject to competition.** There were two regimes: The main experimental system was deprived of light
 292 rhythmicity, *i.e.*, both the host plants (sown, grown, and infested) and the aphids were raised under
 293 complete darkness (0h Day:24h Night). In total there were 360 aphids = Alone as a single clone (3 aphid
 294 clones X 6 repeats X 10 aphid 2nd instars per microcosm) + Competition (3 competition scenarios X 6
 295 repeats X [5+5] aphid 2nd instars per microcosm). The reference experimental system was the control
 296 under a normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night). We used two pea aphid clones (N116 [baseline] and
 297 N127) and one clone of black bean aphid (BB). The bars represent the aphid reproductive success (total
 298 aphid numbers in the microcosm, mean \pm SE) under normal light-dark cycle (light grey), (N116, n = 3,
 299 N127, n = 3, BB, n = 3), and constant darkness (dark grey), (N116, n = 6, N127, n = 6, BB, n = 6). The
 300 aphid clones were present either as respective single clones or in pair-wise competition on the faba bean
 301 host plant in the microcosm: alone or in intraspecific competition with (N127 vs N116), or in interspecific
 302 competition (N116 vs BB and N127 vs BB).
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319 **Table S3. Model (GLM3), a test of aphid reproductive success under normal dark/light conditions**
320 **or complete darkness, with and without competition.** Analysis of deviance table (Type II tests)
321 displaying the significance of the main effects tested in the Model (GLM3, with a quasipoisson family). The
322 predictors were: Light regime (a categorical variable of two levels (normal Light-dark cycle [baseline], and
323 constant darkness), Aphid clone (a categorical variable of three 3 levels (pea aphidN116 [baseline],
324 conspecific N127, and heterospecific BB), Aphid interaction status (a categorical variable of three 3 levels
325 (perfuming alone, intraspecific competition, interspecific competition), The interaction (Light regime X
326 Aphid clone), The interaction (Light regime X Aphid interaction status), The interaction (Aphid clone X
327 Aphid interaction status), Shoot:Root dry weight (SRW), a numerical covariate variable,), and Competitor
328 density (a numerical variable representing the total numbers of the respective competing aphid clone in
329 the microcosm). Aphid reproductive success (total aphid numbers in the microcosm on the 11th day) was
330 the response variable. The total numbers pertaining to the aphids present as single clones in the
331 microcosm were halved as the starting population was 10 instars, while the starting population for the
332 competition interaction was 5 instars for each competitor clone. The main effects are shown using an
333 Anova command. Significant results are shown in bold. There were two regimes: The main experimental
334 system was deprived of light rhythmicity, *i.e.*, both the host plants (sown, grown, and infested) and the
335 aphids were raised under complete darkness (0h Day:24h Night). In total there were 360 aphids = Single
336 clones (3 aphid clones X 6 repeats X 10 aphid 2nd instars per microcosm) + Competition (3 competition
337 scenarios X 6 repeats X [5+5] aphid 2nd instars per microcosm). The reference experimental system was
338 the control under a normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night). We used two pea aphid clones (N116
339 [baseline] and N127) and one clone of black bean aphid (BB).

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	Sum Sq	Df	F value	Pr(>F)
SRW	68.51	1	3.92	0.052
Competitive Pressure	2.22	1	0.13	0.723
Light Regime	311.51	1	17.82	< 0.0001
Aphid clone	159.38	2	4.56	0.014
Aphid interaction status	36.75	2	1.05	0.355
Light Regime X Aphid clone	321.67	2	9.2	0.0003
Light Regime X Aphid interaction status	124.66	2	3.56	0.034
Aphid clone X Aphid interaction status	117.71	3	2.24	0.091
Residuals	1153.61	66		

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Fig S17. C:N ratios in the host plant and the pea aphid clones (N116 and N127) and black bean aphid clone (BB) in response to reproductive success under normal dark/light conditions or complete darkness, subject to competition. There were two regimes: The main experimental system was deprived of light rhythmicity, *i.e.*, both the host plants (sown, grown, and infested) and the aphids were raised under complete darkness (0h Day:24h Night). In total there were 360 aphids = Alone as a single clone (3 aphid clones X 6 repeats X 10 aphid 2nd instars per microcosm) + Competition (3 competition scenarios X 6 repeats X [5+5] aphid 2nd instars per microcosm). The reference experimental system was the control under a normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night). We used two pea aphid clones (N116 [baseline] and N127) and one clone of black bean aphid (BB). The bars represent the values of C:N ratios of the faba bean host plant (left) and the aphid clones (right); normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night), referred to as (L), and constant darkness (0h Day:24h Night), referred to as (NL). The aphids were present on the faba bean host in the microcosm as respective single clones, or in pair-wise competition: alone (single clone), in intraspecific competition (N127 vs N116), or interspecific competition (N116 vs BB and N127 vs BB).

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Fig S18. Host plant dry weight in response to normal dark/light conditions or complete darkness and aphid presence (alone or in competition). There were two regimes: The main experimental system was deprived of light rhythmicity, *i.e.*, both the host plants (sown, grown, and infested) and the aphids were raised under complete darkness (0h Day:24h Night). In total there were 360 aphids = Alone as a single clone (3 aphid clones X 6 repeats X 10 aphid 2nd instars per microcosm) + Competition (3 competition scenarios X 6 repeats X [5+5] aphid 2nd instars per microcosm). The reference experimental system was the control under a normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night). We used two pea aphid clones (N116 [baseline] and N127) and one clone of black bean aphid (BB). The bars represent the means (\pm SE) for the dry weight of the host plant per microcosm across treatments at the end of the experiment; under a normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night), referred to as (L), and constant darkness (0h Day:24h Night), referred to as (NL). The enveloped number on top of the bar represents the aphid burden on the plant (the total numbers of aphids in the single clone scenarios, or the total numbers of both competing aphid clones in the competition scenarios). The aphids were present as respective single clones, or in pair-wise competition on the faba bean host: alone, or intraspecific competition with (N127 vs N116), or in interspecific competition (N116 vs BB and N127 vs BB).

434 **Table S5. Model (GLM5), a test of the differences in the host plant shoot length at the beginning**
435 **and the end of the experiment, subject to normal dark/light conditions or complete darkness and**
436 **with/without the presence of aphid competition.** Analysis of deviance table (Type II tests) displaying
437 the significance of the main effects tested in the Model (GLM5, with a quasipoisson family). The predictors
438 were: Light regime (a categorical variable of two levels (normal Light-dark cycle [baseline], and constant
439 darkness), Aphid clone (a categorical variable of three 3 levels (pea aphidN116 [baseline], conspecific
440 N127, and heterospecific BB, where the respective clones were present alone in the microcosm), Aphid
441 interaction status (a categorical variable of three 3 levels (alone as a single clone, intraspecific competition,
442 interspecific competition), Aphid burden (a numerical variable representing the total numbers of both
443 competing aphid clones on the plant, and all possible interactions between the predictors. The difference
444 in the length of the shoot of the host plant between the beginning and the end of the experiment on Day
445 11 was the response variable. The main effects are shown using an Anova command. Significant results
446 are shown in bold. There were two regimes: The main experimental system was deprived of light
447 rhythmicity, *i.e.*, both the host plants (sown, grown, and infested) and the aphids were raised under
448 complete darkness (0h Day:24h Night). In total there were 360 aphids = Alone as a single clone (3 aphid
449 clones X 6 repeats X 10 aphid 2nd instars per microcosm) + Competition (3 competition scenarios X 6
450 repeats X [5+5] aphid 2nd instars per microcosm). The reference experimental system was the control
451 under a normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night). We used two pea aphid clones (N116 [baseline] and
452 N127) and one clone of black bean aphid (BB).

	Sum Sq	Df	F value	Pr(>F)
Aphid burden	7.90	1	0.59	0.444
Light regime	181.76	1	13.68	0.0005
Aphid clone	13.73	2	0.52	0.600
Aphid interaction status	234.82	2	8.84	0.0005
Aphid burden X Light regime	0.31	1	0.02	0.880
Aphid burden X Aphid clone	44.79	2	1.69	0.196
Light regime X Aphid clone	0.81	2	0.03	0.970
Aphid burden X Aphid interaction status	218.34	2	8.22	0.0008
Light regime X Aphid interaction status	8.44	2	0.32	0.729
Aphid clone X Aphid interaction status	29.09	3	0.73	0.539
Aphid burden X Light regime X Aphid clone	17.04	2	0.64	0.531
Aphid burden X Light regime X Aphid interaction status	4.51	2	0.17	0.844
Aphid burden X Aphid clone X Aphid interaction status	27.96	3	0.70	0.556
Light regime X Aphid clone X Aphid interaction status	11.41	3	0.29	0.835
Aphid burden X Light regime X Aphid clone X Aphid interaction status	11.67	3	0.29	0.830
Residuals	650.88	49		

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Fig S19. Shoot length to root length of the host plant in response to normal dark/light conditions or complete darkness and aphid presence (alone or in competition). There were two regimes: The main experimental system was deprived of light rhythmicity, *i.e.*, both the host plants (sown, grown, and infested) and the aphids were raised under complete darkness (0h Day:24h Night). In total there were 360 aphids = Alone as a single clone (3 aphid clones X 6 repeats X 10 aphid 2nd instars per microcosm) + Competition (3 competition scenarios X 6 repeats X [5+5] aphid 2nd instars per microcosm). The reference experimental system was the control under a normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night). We used two pea aphid clones (N116 [baseline] and N127) and one clone of black bean aphid (BB). The bars represent the means (\pm SE) for the ratio of shoot length to root length of the host plant per microcosm across treatments at the end of the experiment; under a normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night), referred to as (L), and constant darkness (0h Day:24h Night), referred to as (NL). The enveloped number on top of the bar represents the aphid burden on the plant (the total numbers of aphids in the single clone scenarios, or the total numbers of both competing aphid clones in the competition scenarios). The aphid clones were present on the faba bean host in the microcosm: alone or in intraspecific competition with (N127 vs N116), or in interspecific competition (N116 vs BB and N127 vs BB).

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Table S6. Model (GLM6), a test of the shoot:root length of the host plant at the end of the experiment under normal dark/light conditions or complete darkness, with/without the presence of aphid competition. Analysis of deviance table (Type II tests) displaying the significance of the main effects tested in the Model (GLM6, with a quasibinomial family). The predictors were: Light regime (a categorical variable of two levels (normal Light-dark cycle [baseline], and constant darkness), Aphid clone (a categorical variable of three 3 levels (pea aphidN116 [baseline], conspecific N127, and heterospecific BB, where the respective clones were present alone in the microcosm), Aphid interaction status (a categorical variable of three 3 levels (alone as a single clone, intraspecific competition, interspecific competition), Aphid burden (a numerical variable representing the total numbers of both competing aphid clones on the plant, and all possible interaction between the predictors. The ratio of the shoot length to the root length of the host plant per microcosm at the end of the experiment on Day 11 was the response variable. The main effects are shown using an Anova command. Significant results are shown in bold. There were two regimes: The main experimental system was deprived of light rhythmicity, *i.e.*, both the host plants (sown, grown, and infested) and the aphids were raised under complete darkness (0h Day:24h Night). In total there were 360 aphids = Alone (3 aphid clones X 6 repeats X 10 aphid 2nd instars per microcosm) + Competition (3 competition scenarios X 6 repeats X [5+5] aphid 2nd instars per microcosm). The reference experimental system was the control under a normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night). We used two pea aphid clones (N116 [baseline] and N127) and one clone of black bean aphid (BB). The aphid clones were present on the faba bean host in the microcosm: alone or in intraspecific competition with (N127 vs N116), or in interspecific competition (N116 vs BB and N127 vs BB).

	Sum Sq	Df	F value	Pr(>F)
Aphid burden	4.48	1	1.59	0.214
Light regime	49.07	1	17.38	0.0001
Aphid clone	1.50	2	0.27	0.768
Aphid interaction status	19.76	2	3.50	0.038
Aphid burden X Light regime	4.87	1	1.72	0.195
Aphid burden X Aphid clone	2.84	2	0.50	0.608
Light regime X Aphid clone	2.64	2	0.47	0.630
Aphid burden X Aphid interaction status	12.54	2	2.22	0.119
Light regime X Aphid interaction status	4.44	2	0.79	0.461
Aphid clone X Aphid interaction status	3.71	3	0.44	0.727
Aphid burden X Light regime X Aphid clone	1.50	2	0.27	0.767
Aphid burden X Light regime X Aphid interaction status	1.38	2	0.24	0.784
Aphid burden X Aphid clone X Aphid interaction status	1.01	3	0.12	0.948
Light regime X Aphid clone X Aphid interaction status	5.06	3	0.560	0.620
Aphid burden X Light regime X Aphid clone X Aphid interaction status	4.61	3	0.54	0.654
Residuals	138.34	49		

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Fig S20. Shoot length difference between the beginning and the end of the experiment in response to under normal dark/light conditions or complete darkness and aphid presence (alone or in competition). There were two regimes: The main experimental system was deprived of light rhythmicity, *i.e.*, both the host plants (sown, grown, and infested) and the aphids were raised under complete darkness (0h Day:24h Night). In total there were 360 aphids = Alone as a single clone (3 aphid clones X 6 repeats X 10 aphid 2nd instars per microcosm) + Competition (3 competition scenarios X 6 repeats X [5+5] aphid 2nd instars per microcosm). The reference experimental system was the control under a normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night). We used two pea aphid clones (N116 [baseline] and N127) and one clone of black bean aphid (BB). The bars represent the means (\pm SE) for the per cent of length difference of the host plant shoot between the beginning and the end of the experiment per microcosm across treatments at the end of the experiment; under a normal light-dark cycle (16h Day:8h Night), referred to as (L), and constant darkness (0h Day:24h Night), referred to as (NL). The enveloped number on top of the bar represents the aphid burden on the plant (the total numbers of aphids in the single clone scenarios, or the total numbers of both competing aphid clones in the competition scenarios). The aphid clones were present on the faba bean host in the microcosm: alone or in intraspecific competition with (N127 vs N116), or in interspecific competition (N116 vs BB and N127 vs BB).

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Fig S21. Western blot gel for HSP70. The image displays the outcome of western blot gel for HSP70 across the different treatment lines. Left to right, Lane 2 = N116 light condition (L), Lane 3 = N116 no light condition (NL), Lane 4 = N127 light condition (L), Lane 5 = N127= no light condition (NL), Lane 6 = BB light condition (L), Lane 7 = BB no light condition (NL), Lane 8 = N116 vs N127 light condition (L), Lane 9 = N116 vs N127 no light condition (NL), Lane 10 = N116 vs BB light condition (L), Lane 11 = N116 vs BB no light condition (NL).

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